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The role of infrastructures in the Smart Mobility era

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Our lives are becoming 'Smart': we enjoy smartphones, our urban environments are evolving into Smart Cities and our automobiles are incorporating 'smart' features assisting our driving and increasing our safety. In this context, transportation infrastructures should also become smarter, as they are a key player in a changing world, more competitive and cohesive every day.

With some minor geographical exceptions, in general people and goods will be moving around the globe further and faster. Roads being the essential link in the modal chain, transportation systems will become fully integrated and intermodal, allowing travellers and freight to switch seamlessly between modes and across borders. All major airports and seaports will connect to the rail network; intermodal terminals for passenger and freight should be "smartly" designed and equipped accordingly. In the case of freight, cooperative systems, seamless transshipment and smart route design will lead to the sector's optimization.

Needless to say, the world needs intelligent infrastructures that are able to process the vast amount of information collected in real time and provide the most effective transportation services to businesses and citizens alike.

'BRICKS' INFRASTRUCTURES BECOME SMART

New ideas, pioneering strategies and entrepreneurship are needed to respond to this new reality. Thanks to recent technological innovations,

such as remote sensing, advance analytics, automated operations, crowdsourcing and integrated scheduling and control, traditional 'bricks' infrastructure can now be used more effectively, and operated and maintained more efficiently.

The establishment of an integrated transportation 'info-structure', relying on V2I (vehicle to infrastructure), I2V (infrastructure to vehicle) and V2V (vehicle to vehicle) and I2I (infrastructure to infrastructure) communications, but also on the availability of open and quality transportation data, will provide substantial improvements for the performance of transportation networks and raise its efficiency. At the same time, location-based and traffic-related services will allow robust built-in data privacy and security solutions.

NO SMART CITY WITHOUT SMART MOBILITY

All around the world people are thronging in and to cities. Some 53 per cent of the population currently lives in

urban areas and by 2050 this number is expected to reach 67 per cent. Countless studies have stood out that most cities are badly equipped to cope with the transportation challenges ahead.

In addition to the increasing demand for urban mobility, needs are evolving. Changing travel habits, demand for services to increase convenience, speed and predictability, as well as evolving customer expectations towards customization, will require more intelligent infrastructure able to cope with these extended mobility requirements. The equation is clear: there cannot be a Smart City without Smart Mobility, and no Smart Mobility is possible without Smart Infrastructure.

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VISUALISING SMART TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURES

'Smart Transportation Infrastructures: A Look into the Future' is a whiteboard animation presenting the four key attributes of the Smart Transportation Infrastructures of the Future: Mobility, Intelligence, Safety & Security and Sustainability. The video clip reviews the main challenges towards the deployment of a new generation of Transportation Infrastructures connecting people and businesses across the world.

I invite *Thinking Highways* readers to watch it on STA's YouTube channel at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7MGfYJLLjps>

